

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight

A534

7 April 1997

OXICOA

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. A 534

DATE: 07 104 1977

Take off : 1035

Landing : 1820

Aircraft Scientist : KAYE
Flight Leader : PERCIVAL
Others : DEWEY
KENT
PICKERING
RICHER
BANDY
PENKETT
LAW
BAUGUITTE
MILLS
TIDDEMAN
GREEN

Captain : FLT Lt PURSE
Co-pilot : FLT Lt THORNHILL
Navigator : FLT Lt MORRIS
Engineer : MENG QUICH
Loadmaster : FLT Lt CANNING.

Trials Instructions TACIA / ACSOE :

Operating area : NORTH WEST QUADRANT OF THE SANTA MARIA FIR

General synoptic situation

TIME :

POST FLIGHT REQUIREMENTS FORM

Flight No: 53.4

Date: 07.04.97

A/S Name: AKAYE

Aircraft Scientist's Post Flight Requirements:

1. Are any copies of the flight folder required?
YES NO for5.....

2. Flight data and folders will normally be discarded after 10 years, is this OK?
YES NO If not OK, state period

3. Is the flight part of an international project or major campaign?
YES NO Name of ProjectACSOE.....

4. Do you want the video tape kept?
YES NO How long?10 YRS.....

5. Has the Handheld camera or the Camcorder been used:
YES NO
If yes, do you want the handheld camera film processed:
immediately or when the film is finished?

6. Do you want the cloud physics data kept?
YES NO
If yes, which disc / file do you want it stored in?TO BE ADVISED.....

7. Do you want to do the interactive processing?
YES NO

NOTE:

- Members of MRF Radiation and Cloud Physics groups are expected to meet their own requirements for data storage and non-standard processing.
- For non MRF users, Data Management Section will keep the processed data TEMPORARILY until the requirements are made known.
- Any other requirements for post-flight processing and data storage should be discussed with the Data Management Section.
- If copies of the Flight Folder are required, it is the responsibility of the Aircraft Scientist / User to produce them.

OXICOA: Remote Ocean Ozone

SORTIE OBJECTIVE:

To observe the atmospheric chemical composition in the remote Atlantic. The data will be added to a systematically collected airmass data base. The data base will be used to determine the oxidising capacity and the budget of tropospheric oxidants in marine air at mid latitudes in the northern hemisphere..

LOCATION: North Atlantic Ocean

WEATHER: Cloud Free

FLIGHT PATTERN:

- [1] Depart Santa Maria and transit to sampling area at convenient altitude. ~~4131150~~
 - [1.1] Hold climb at 3000 ft for wet chemistry check. ~~4111370~~
 - [1.2] 15 minute run (above boundary layer, speed 180) for NOxy Calibration.
 - [2] Stepped profile descent from approx. FL260 to 50ft (or minimum safe altitude) ~~944W~~
 — 1000ft/min until approx. FL70 then 500ft/min. ~~39~~
 - [3] Profile stack at levels determined from descent. 15 minute runs at top and bottom of stack, 10 minute runs at intermediate levels.
-
- [4] Transit to location of second stack. ~~4131150~~
 - [5] Stepped profile descent from approx. FL260 to 50ft (or minimum safe altitude) ~~42 45~~
 — 1000ft/min until approx. FL70 then 500ft/min.
 - [6] Profile stack at levels determined from descent. 15 minute runs at top and bottom of stack, 10 minute runs at intermediate levels.
-
- [7] Transit to location of ~~second~~ ^{third} stack. ~~4131150~~
 - [8] Stepped profile descent from approx. FL260 to 50ft (or minimum safe altitude) ~~42 45~~
 — 1000ft/min until approx. FL70 then 500ft/min.
 - [9] Profile stack at levels determined from descent. 15 minute runs at top and bottom of stack, 10 minute runs at intermediate levels.
-
- [10] Transit to Santa Maria as convenient.
 [10.1] 15 minute run (above boundary layer, speed 180 kts) for NOxy Calibration.

OTHER REQUIREMENTS:

Cabin pressure and temperature to be kept constant on level runs.

A534 07-APR-97 10:36:05-18:16:45GMT

INS TRACK - run no

A534 07-APR-97 Height time series

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A. Kaye*

Project: ASOE Date: 7/4/97

Flight No: A534 Page | of 5

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
10:39:48	11	R1	3000	P	300	37.12	-25.40	hazy scattered cu ahead	
10:48:13	12	R1	3000	P	309	37.28	-25.81	fields of small cu ahead	
10:53:48			99	F	304	37.43	-26.09	very dry level on the tephigram. ^{aerobols dropped} at the same level.	
10:16:45			100	F	295	38.05	-27.45	edge clear to climb. NO NO ₂ NO _{y2} calibrated	
11:31:40	15	R2	200	F	296	38.66	-28.96	High level Run @ 220 Kts. 11:31:40	
11:43:10		R2	200	F	294				
11:50:12		R2	200	F	293	39.09	-30.05	Alto cu ahead small cu fields below. clear above.	
12:07:12		R2	200	F	305	39.76	-31.57	streets of small ^(fields) cu below Alto cu at about our level & clear above.	
12:17:00		R2	200	F	303	40.28	-32.39	fields of small cu below almost in a thin deck of clouds clear above that cloud.	
12:25:45		R2	200	F	302	40.68	-33.01	cloud at this level thicker, ^{12:50 13:05 13:55} Patches of small cu near surface.	
12:29:07									
12:41:34		R2	200	F	302	41.44	-34.36	complex cu structure below flying at our level lots of interesting thing at our level.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: KSOE

Date: 7/14/97

Aircraft Scientist: R. Kays

Flight No: A 534

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height		INS	Omega		Other Info. (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
			Pres/Rad	FL		Latitude	Longitude	
12:57:15		R2	200	F	306	42.22	-35.70	clearing ahead complex cloud below to right clear above.
13:05:03		R2/ R2	200	F	304	42.64	-36.38	broken SC above above ahead hazy some on near surface & hazy.
13:05:50		R2.2	200	F	304	42.64		
13:13:43		R2.2	200	F	300	43.00	-37.00	clear below overcast above. —
13:27:33		R2.2 P2	200	F	297	43.55	-38.04	clear above & Below Solid was of SC Ahead ^{Out}
13:31:11								interrupt profile. &
								weaving @ 25.2k to turn.
13:38:35		P1	250	F	86	44.16	-37.97	
13:40:57		P2/R3	224	F	224	44.01	-37.92	hazy cloud to left and right. air traffic at 10 o'clock short contrail.
13:48:11		P3	224	F	225	43.71	-38.29	hazy ahead clear above solid band of cu to the right. (small cloud to the left.)
14:06:56		P3 ¹⁰⁰⁰ ₅₀₀	657 225	F	317			Moist layer transition. F180 10000ft 10000ft
14:14:20								
14:18:36		P3						1018 seaslope 4

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: A534

Date: 7/9/97

Aircraft Scientist: A. Keye

Flight No: AC50E

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height		INS	Omega		Other Info. (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
			Pres/Rad	FL		Latitude	Longitude	
14:10:48	25	R4	100	R	30	43.7 -38.8	clear some small etc	100, 1000, 6000, 11000, 15000, 18000, 21000 (170)
14:28:06	26	R4/P41	100	R	28	44.02 -38.64		
14:30:28	27	P4.1/R5	1000	P	210	43.97 -38.57	hazy clear above.	(4) 2:30
14:38:25	28	P.5/P4.2	1000	P	286	43.62 -38.83		
14:42:41	2008	P.4.2/R5	6000	P	208			
14:54:44	2108	R5/P4.2	6000	P	248	42.87 -39.33	base layer. is solid bank of cloud ahead. clear above and below.	
14:59:20	2208	P4.2/R5	110	F	39	43.10 -39.25	Solid bank of cu to left clear above and below hazy.	
15:07:36	32	P4/P4.4	110	F	74	43.61 -38.67	' ''	<u>FL 170</u>
15:11:28		P4.4						
15:13:20	34	R8	150	F	211	43.67 -38.57	Solid cu bank to left ^{wright} confused to cloud to right ^{left}	
15:22:34	35	R8/P4.5	150	F	212	43.22 -38.93	will keep running to end of profile.	NO & NO ₂ [Nay failed]
							lower BBR JNO ₂ all off scale. 30min.	
15:25:09		R4.5e						

(25)
(6) 6:46
(30)

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: 534

Date: 7/14/1977

Aircraft Scientist: G. Cuye.

Flight No: ACS06

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height		INS	Omega		Other Info. (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
			Pres/Rad	FL		Latitude	Longitude	
15:26:30	37	R9	180	P	35	45.16	-58.90	cloud as before Lower BBR's gone!
15:33:30	38	R9/126	180	F	50	43.55	-38.53	Streets of cu to Right. high cloud ahead.
15:36:41	39	P4.6/R10	210	F	103	43.53	-38.19	
15:40:18	40	R10	210	F				Front very clearly visible ahead.
15:44:42	41	R11	170	F	108	43.37	-37.23	"
								15:58 20minuted - 37 bags in first profile 300 second profile
								20 bags in second profile.
16:09:07		R11	170	F	122	42.79	-34.31	Complex structure ahead right left turbulence overcast above.
16:13:40		R11	170	F	122	42.59	-33.81	Broken cu ahead.
16:11:32	43	F/P5	170	F	122	42.59	-33.29	"
16:30:18		P5	500	P	116	42.06	-32.48	change rate to 500 fpm @ cloud tops.
16:37:36		P5	1600	P	115	41.92	-32.00	3/8 sc above hazy.
16:40:09		P5c	50	R	132	41.85	-31.70	1022 sea state 5.

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: ACSoE

Date: 7/4/97

Aircraft Scientist: R. Kaye.

Flight No: A534

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height		INS	Omega		Other Info. (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
			Pres/Rad	FL		Latitude	Longitude	
		R12	600	P				Noxy zero.
16:12:43		R12e	600	P	127	41.76	-31.77	Broken sc Sc deck at 2K and another above.
17:16:40			708	F	163	39.94	-29.40	Sc below some bands of ci above.
17:38:16		-	120	F	120	38.30	-28.19	Decent to Ft 120 — Excellent view of volcano ¹⁸¹⁵ 1805
17:45:40								Problem. ^{Trim} Rudder Runaway. ¹⁷⁵⁰
17:47:01	47	R13	70	F	125	37.93	-27.34	1/8 cu below clear above smooth smooth sea.
17:50:02 17:59:28	48	R13e	70	F	#121.	37.53	-26.56	1/8 ci above, smooth sea no low low cloud.
								<u>END OF SCIENCE</u>

MISSION SCIENTIST'S LOG Project: OXICDA Date: 7/4/97

Mission Scientist: *S. Denbrett*
K. Law

Flight No: 574 Page 1 of 3

GMT	Run No.	Notes:	
10:49:14 (end)	R1	FLO2S	H ₂ O ₂ - 15 ppbv ~ 4000 ft O ₃ - 60 ppbv
11:49	R1	¹⁰⁰ FL 200	Trans. try to NW Azores (45°N, 40°W) Profiling up to 10,000 ft H ₂ O ₂ dropping at 9900 ft → 10,000 ft mod H ₂ O ₂ > meas H ₂ O ₂ at 8500-9000 ft. PBL structure: 2 layers 2500 ft, 9000 ft well above cloud at 10,000 ft O ₃ and H ₂ O ₂ very uniform, little structure mod H ₂ O ₂ med > H ₂ O ₂ meas by 500 ppbv
12:26		¹⁰⁰ FL 200 → FL200	Climbing to FL200 10,000 → 0.52 12,800 → 0.6 13,700 → 0.44 corrected 14,300 → 0.34 14,000 ft → 15,500 → 0.17 500 ft min ⁻¹ → 1500 ft correction corrected 16,700 0.18 (17,800 ft) 18,300 0.61 19,700 0.43 (35.41 O ₃)
12:31:40	R2	Transit to far NW corner of operating area	20,000 0.31, 32.69, NO _y 300 ppbv NO _y 103 high at 10,000 → 13,700 ft Background NO _y 40 ppbv
13:10			O ₃ ~ 30-35 ppbv H ₂ O ₂ → 0.4 NO ₂ 55 ppbv, NO _y ~ 300 ppbv
13:21			LT structure over last 40 mins
13:35			20000 ft Opening through frontal surface high in O ₃ - 75 ppbv, 30 ppbv NO _y 600 ppbv.

① NO_y ② H₂O₂ med H₂O₂ meas
③ H₂O₂ O₃ (4) T-14

MISSION SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project:

Date: 7/4/97

Mission Scientist:

Flight No: 574 Page 2 of 3

GMT	Run No.	Notes:	
	P1	FL200 → F	43.30N 38W Wind 224 degs
13.27.33	P1 ↑	FL200 → 2400	H ₂ O ₂ ↑ O ₃ ↓ NO _y ↓
13.31.11		220	layer high O ₃ (NO _y 80ppbv) → peak
13.32.31	P2 2 ↑	FL220 → 260	low H ₂ O ₂ (0.18) → 1000ppbv.
		→ 13.40.57	NO _y → 40ppbv.
			moist layer 25500ft (??6mb)
13.40.57	R3		O ₃ dropping O ₃ dropping, H ₂ O ₂ low remaining
13.49.03	P3	FL260 → 280	Drafting down to soft-
		240	layer at 24000, H ₂ O ₂ low.
		220	inc O ₃ → 72
		208	O ₃ dropping 60 →
		80 (161) → 140	layers - high O ₃ , H ₂ O ₂ ↑
129		(2) 129 → 49	NO _y 600ppbv, NO → low 10-20ppbv.
		084	O ₃ dropping below
50		084	H ₂ O ₂ inc ↑ in this layer → 1ppbv
		050	O ₃ has dropped
		055	
14.18	P4	FL010	
	P5 4.1	FL ⁰⁰¹ → FLO10	Below BL at 800mb (2000ft)
14.30	R5	FL010	
	P4.2	FLO10 FLO10-060	
	R6	FLO60	- layer seen again - large inc ↑ in H ₂ O ₂ (→ 4ppbv) (thin layer) NO _y as well (→ 1ppbv) MCHO problems at bottom of profile
14.52	P4.3	FLO60 → F110	
	R7	FL110	NO _y high (600ppbv) and O ₃ , H ₂ O ₂

MISSION SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project:

Date: 7/4/97

Mission Scientist:

Flight No: 534 Page 3 of 3

GMT	Run No.	Notes:	
15:11:07	P4.4	FL110 → FL150	NOy high
15:13:28	R8	FL150	Came out of top of P13 layer. 6000m. Positive correlation up to 15 km (near 7000m) Problem with NOy. → then ↓
15:22:31	P4.5	FL180 → FL180	
15:25:22	R9	FL180	
	P4.6	F180 → FL210	
15:40:15 ^{end}	R10	F210 → F170	Modelled + measured H ₂ O ₂ track very well.
16:10	R11		large change in H ₂ O ₂ possibly associated with front
16:15	P5		Start profile down from P13
16:28	P5 start?	16:19:32	good correlation NOy (10)
16:39	R P6?		Anti correlation H ₂ O ₂ /O ₃
16:44	R12?		NO ₂ = NOy was pressing from cloud.
	R13	FL190	Transit lane
17:70			Descent to 12000m

Interactive Processing Log

Flight No. A534 Date: 070497 User: HAYE
Interactive by: D PERCIVAL
Date: 16-04-97

Renav

KALMAN FILTERING CHOSEN

TWC

Profile plotted :

Line chosen : Profile / Whole flight / Other

a = -

b = +

c = +

NO VALID DATA, PROBE FAULT PRE-FLIGHT

LWC

NO PMS DATA READ IN.

OK.

Heimann / Barnes

OK.

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: A534

Date: 07 04 97

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GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
0249	REF +	5	0567	/			Approx 0568
	REF -	7	2855	/			Approx 3071
	AOSS	19	0000	F/S O/S	TORQUE		2047 st. and level
	AOA	18	772	F/S O/S	TORQUE		2047 st. and level
	RD HT	37	0000				As Indicated 0000
	PR HT	8	3883	1008	1009		As Altimeter
	CABP	14	3305	970			
	A/S	9	0001	/			As ASI 0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	0497	120	124		
	UP2S	82	0423	55	61		
	UIRS	83	0191	-360			
	UP1Z	84	0151	/			Approx 0147
	UP2Z	85	146	/			Approx 0149
	UIRZ	86	185	/	3N02		Approx 2061
	UP1T	87	2519	16	18.4		As IAT
	UP2T	88	2525	15			As IAT
	UIRT	89	0000	/	3N02		As IAT
	LP1S	91	146	-2	-2		
	LP2S	92	0120	-3	-9		
	LIRS	93	90	-400	3N02		
	LP1Z	94	152	/			Approx 0150
	LP2Z	95	155	/			Approx 0146
	LIRZ	96	0010		3N02		Approx 2050
	LP1T	97	2647	19	18.5		As IAT
	LP2T	98	2414	20			As IAT
	LIRT	99	0000	/	3N02		As IAT
	J/W	42	996	0-1			As Indicated 0000
	NEPH	47	XXXX				
	HYGR	58	3088	20	20.5		
	HYCC	59	703	/	20		696-901
	FDEW	138	4095				DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C
	FSTA	139	4095				
	DTF	10	1140	19			
	DTC	11	6		19		
	NDTF	23	0374	17			same as De-Iced
	NDTC	24	6				
	INCT	48	2610				
	CCN	140	XXXX				less than 4095 if ON
	TWCD	70	4095				0000-4094
	TSAM	72	0147	/			0640-1860 < min
	O3	100	149				
	O3P	106	2039	960			$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145m.B$
	O3RG	113	1423				
	MIEM	141	2009				
0913	PRTC	142	2374	/			

Flight Leaders' Pre-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
0913	FL NO	1	Hex	0534	1534	✓	Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0091			Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0410	091410	✓	Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	08-09-10	✓		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
18.9 3553	1442 ✓ 3255 ✓	3553	521 ✓	3552	3711 ✓	3553	136 ✓
	LATC	160	Dec	0420	36.96N ✓		Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	3809	24.80W ✓		Longitude
0916							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: PRE FLIGHT

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
0917	TWCD	70	4045			0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	1131	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	156	✓		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2470	✓		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2607	HIGH ?		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	2082	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2126	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1012	✓		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4088	✓		4095	
	EV1V	170	2042				
	EV2V	171	2043				
	NPWR	172	3408				
	EVIC	173	3468				
0923	EV2C	174	3468				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOMES	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large / Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon ⁵ µm		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon ^{1.2} µm		

Flight Leader's ~~FC~~ / In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: A534 Date: 070997

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GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1050	REF +	5	0567	/			Approx 0568
	REF -	7	2853	/			Approx 3071
	AOSS	19	1966	F/S O/S	TORQUE		2047 st. and level
	AOA	18	1063	F/S O/S	TORQUE		2047 st. and level
	RD HT	37	4095	/			As Indicated 0000
	PR HT	8	2750	9.9	FLICR -		As Altimeter
	CABP	14	3196	970	/		
	A/S	9	1409	180	/		As ASI 0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	2207	731	732		
	UP2S	82	1940	360	400		
	UIRS	83	0814	-230	Ino2		
	UP1Z	84	0155	/			Approx 0147
	UP2Z	85	150	/			Approx 0149
	UIRZ	86	0814				Approx 2061
	UP1T	87	2721	6	7.0		As IAT
	UP2T	88	2736	6			As IAT
	UIRT	89	0000	/			As IAT
	LP1S	91	1297	464	SPINING!		
	LP2S	92	0114		"		
	LIRS	93	3464	-50	"		
	LP1Z	94	224	/	"		Approx 0150
	LP2Z	95	0155	/	"		Approx 0146
1132	LIRZ	96	3000 3000	/	CR		Approx 2050
	LP1T	97	3030	-8	-7.1		As IAT
	LP2T	98	3026	-8	/		As IAT
	LIRT	99	0000	/	/		As IAT
	J/W	42	1158	0.0			As Indicated 0000
	NEPH	47	1843				
	HYGR	58	1843	-20	-21.8		
	HYCC	59	741	/			696-901
	FDEW	138	1525	-23.75			DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C
	FSTA	139	992				
	DTF	10	2624	-7	-18.4		
	DTC	11	4		-7.2		
	NDTF	23	2274	-8	-18.7		same as De-Iced
	NDTC	24	4				
	INCT	48	2626				
	CCN	140	4095				less than 4095 if ON
	TWCD	70	4095	-OFF	/		0000-4094
	TSAM	72	4095				0640-1860 < min
	O3	100	0095				
	O3P	106	1672	813.8			$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$
	O3RG	113	1935				
	HIEM	141	2442				
1150	PRTC	142	2380	/			

H-CHCS
H-DOR

Flight Leaders' ~~Pge~~ (In-Flight) Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
				534			
1150	FL NO	1	Hex	780	A534	/	Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0115			Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0137	115153		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	0015	/		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
^{-13.6} 2254	1260 ✓ 3855 ✓	2250	1482	2255	3785 ✓	2253	173 ✓
	LATC	160	Dec	445	39.16 N	//	Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	3750	-30 W	//	Longitude
1154							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: FL200 .

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1201	TWCD	70	4095	/		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	2502			2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	1205			0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2529			2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2211			2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	399			0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	1664			0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1030	/		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4094			4095	
	EV1V	170	3476				
	EV2V	171	3137				
	NPWR	172	2719				
	EVIC	173	4016				
1209	EV2C	174	4001				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: A534

Date: 070497

Page 3 of 4

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1242	REF +	5	567	/			Approx 0568
	REF -	7	2853	/			Approx 3071
	AOSS	19	1912	/ F/S O/S	TORQUE		2047 st. and level
	AOA	18	1735	/ F/S O/S	TORQUE		2047 st. and level
	RD HT	37	4095	FL200	/		As Indicated 0000
	PR HT	8	1795	20.0	FL200 /		As Altimeter
	CABP	14	2795	850			
	A/S	9	2032	225	/		As ASI 0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	1628	520	516		
	UP2S	82	1414	255	252		
	UIRS	83	704	-263	3N02		
	UP1Z	84	149	/			Approx 0147
	UP2Z	85	143	/			Approx 0149
	UIRZ	86	773		3N02		Approx 2061
	UP1T	87	3071	-10	-9.3		As IAT
	UP2T	88	3086	-11			As IAT
	UIRT	89	0000		3N02		As IAT
	LP1S	91	274	55	51		
	LP2S	92	180	814	8		
	LIRS	93	298	1558	3N02		
	LP1Z	94	150	/			Approx 0150
	LP2Z	95	150	/			Approx 0146
	LIRZ	96	320	/	3N02		Approx 2050
	LP1T	97	3106	-12			As IAT
	LP2T	98	304	-12	-10.6		As IAT
	LIRT	99	0000		3N02		As IAT
	J/W	42	1159	08.00			As Indicated 0000
	NEPH	47	XXXX				
	HYGR	58	1739	-24	-23.1		
	HYCC	59	738				696-901
	FDEW	138	1460	-27	/ -26		DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C
	FSTA	139	928				
	DTF	10	1558	-11			
	DTC	11	4				
	NDTF	23	1371	-27			same as De-Iced
	NDTC	24	3				
	INCT	48	2737				
	CCN	140	XXXX				less than 4095 if ON
	TWCD	70	4095				0000-4094
	TSAM	72	4095				0640-1860 < min
	O3	100	160				
	O3P	106	1660	204			$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$
	O3RG	113	1755				
	HEM	141	2443				
1321	PRTC	142	2379	/			

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
1333	FL NO	1	Hex	534	A534	/	Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0133			Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0431	133431	OFF	Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	0020	✓		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
-27 1710	3254 1260	1712	2113	1702	3220	1622	170 ✓
	LATC	160	Dec	500	44' N ✓		Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	3662	-37.7044		Longitude
1336							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height:

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70				0001-4095	
	TNOS	71				2000-3460 < min	
	TSAM	72				0640-1860 < min	
	TAMB	73				2400-3200	
	TSRC	74				2160-2470	
	HTR1	75				0000-4095 < 4095	
	HTR2	76				0000-4095 < 4095	
	ISRC	77				0001-1230 < min	
	STAT	78				4095	
	EV1V	170					
	EV2V	171					
	NPWR	172					
	EVIC	173					
	EV2C	174					

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOMES	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's Pre In-Flight Check List

1817

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: A534 Date: 070447

Page 1 of 4

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1551	REF +	5	567	/		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2853	/		Approx 3071	
	AOSS	19	1985	/ F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	1964	/ F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	4095	/		As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8	2033	170	17.0	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	3092	938	/		
	A/S	9	2382	237	/	As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	2425	820	705		
	UP2S	82	1734	317	379		
	UIRS	83	0975	/	3N02		
	UP1Z	84	149	/		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	142	/		Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	873	/		Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	2972	-6	-4.6	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2984	-6		As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0000			As IAT	
	LP1S	91	404	101	-1517		
	LP2S	92	4095				
	LIRS	93	4095				
	LP1Z	94	4095			Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	4095			Approx 0146	
	LIRZ	96	4095			Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	4095			As IAT	
	LP2T	98	4095			As IAT	
	LIRT	99	4095			As IAT	
	J/W	42	1142	0.1	0.00	As Indicated 0000	
	NEPH	47	1142				
	HYGR	58	1497	-30.4			
	HYCC	59	723	/		696-901	
	FDEW	138	1449	-27.55	/	DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	493				
	DTF	10	3424	-5	-16.5		
	DTC	11	4		-3.6		
	NDTF	23	3218	-4	-16.4	same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	4				
	INCT	48	2603				
	CCN	140	4095			less than 4095 if ON	
	TWCD	70	4095			0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	4095			0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	190				
	O3P	106	1864	892.6	/	$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3RG	113	1544				
	HEIM	141	2138				
1623	PRC	142	2372				

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
1658	FL NO	1	Hex	534	A534	/	Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0165			Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0850	115850	/	Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	46	/		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
2474 -32	3854 1260	2477	1220	2474	3765	2474	174 /
	LATC	160	Dec	467	41.096		Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	3751	-29.912		Longitude
170							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height:

OFF

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70				0001-4095	
	TNOS	71				2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72				0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73				2400-3200	
	TSRC	74				2160-2470	
	HTR1	75				0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76				0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77				0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78				4095	
	EV1V	170					
	EV2V	171					
	NPWR	172					
	EVIC	173					
	EV2C	174					

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOMES	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 534.....

Date 07-06-97.....

Page 1..... of 2.....

Video Tape
Io. A534
inds 1430
FC / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	36° 58-30N	36° 57.28N
Long	025° 09.86W	25° 09.86W
Time	0843	0843
Status	OK	GC ALIGN

DRS recording to HORACE	(y/n)
HORACE recording to disc	(y/n)
SATCOM sending pos. reports	(y/n)

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
02054				DATA		ON			
01709				SWITCH TO NAV					
23605				TAKE OFF		SANTA MARIA			
				START RUN 1					
23938	11	3000	1020	315	189	8.1	9.7	OFF	003/6
				END RUN 1					
4813	12	3000	1020	315	185	10.6	2.2	OFF	04/6
				Climb	FL100		-CALC		
25414	13	FL100	1013	315	180	0.2	-23.7	OFF	317/7
				Leave	FL100				
1655	14	FL100	1013	310	180	0.7	-25.1	OFF	274/9
				Level	TRANSIT		START	R 2.1	
3140	15	FL200	1013	310	190	-18.5	-20.4	OFF	277/20
				END	RUN	2.1	1		
501	16	FL200	1013	320	220	-22.6	-22.8	OFF	228/14
				START		R 2.2			
554	17	FL200	1013	320	180	-22.8	-24.6	OFF	221/15

Video Tape

No. ~~47~~ A534 #1
Ends 1430.

FFC / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	42°46.8W	42°46.71N
Long	36°32.71W	36°34.45W
Time	1307	1308
Status	OK	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE (y/n)
HORACE recording to disc (y/n)
SATCOM sending pos reports (y/n)

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/Sea-st
				END	RUN	2.2	/START	P1	500 FPM
32733	18	FL200	1013	320	180	-25.2	-40.6	OFF	222/14
		END							
		Hgt	END	START	P1				
33111	19	FL220	1013	320	180	-29.4	-35.5	OFF	229/15
				START	P2				
3201	20	FL220	1013	045	180	-30.1	-40.9	240/15	OFF
		END		END	P2				
4057	21	FL280	1013	240	180	-37.6	-44.3	OFF	235/33
0640	23								
04804	22	FL260	1013	240	180	-37.8	-44.3	OFF	1000m 214/5
0640	23	FL066	1013	045	180	2.2	0.7	OFF	500 FPM 216/6
		50 FPM		END	P3				
1838	24	F078	1018	050	180	16	14.5	OFF	55-6 196/8
1910	25	1000 ^R	1018	045	185	15.8	14.3	OFF	202/7
				END	R4	//	START P4-1		
2805	26	1000 ^R	1018	050	180	15.7	14.1	OFF	205/8
				END	P4-1	//	START R5		
3028	27	1000 ^R	1018	230	180	13.4	12.9	OFF	236/8
				END	R5	//	START P	40.2	1300 FPM
3800	28	1000 ^R	1018	230	180	13.5	12.2	OFF	238/7

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 534

Date 07 04 97

Page 2 of 2

Video Tape	
No. A 534+42	Ends 1730
FFC / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	43° 23.91	43° 21.36 N
Long	38° 57.75W	38° 59.51W
Time	14 44	1445
Status	OK	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	☒ y / ☐ n
HORACE recording to disc	☒ y / ☐ n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	☒ y / ☐ n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
				END	P4.2	/	START R6		
144234	29	6000 ^{ft}	1018	230	180	2.5	1.2	OFF	257/7
				END	R6	/	START	P4.3	1500 ^{ft}
45442	30	6000 ^{ft}	1018	230	180	2.4	0.3	OFF	258/6
				END	P4.3	/	START	R7	
45921	31	FL110	1013	060	185	-4.7	-25.1	OFF	218/9
				END	R7	/	START	P4.4	
150736	32	FL110	1013	060	180	-4.7	-24.5	OFF	219/11
				END	P4.4	/	START	R8	
51128	37	FL150	1013	045	180	-13.5	-36.4	OFF	221/14
				START	R8				
51321	34	FL150	1013	230	180	-13.0	-36.6	OFF	227/12
				END	R8	/	START	P4.5	
52231	35	FL150	1013	230	190	-13.2	-35.2	OFF	217/10
				END	P4.5	/			
52507	36	FL180	1013	230	180	-14.5	-35	OFF	219/11
				START	R9				
52631	37	FL180	1013	055	180	-19.6	-34.1	OFF	221/11
				END	R9	/	START	P4.6	
53371	38	FL180	1013	055	180	-19.7	-34.6	OFF	229/13

Video Tape
 No. A534 #2
 Ends 1730
 (FFC) / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	43° 27.58 N	43° 26.10 W
Long	37° 41.71 W	37° 37.85 W
Time	15 41.24	154200
Status	OK	NAV.

DRS recording to HORACE y/n
 HORACE recording to disc y/n
 SATCOM sending pos reports y/n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/Sea st.
				END	PH-6	/START R 10			
15346	34	FL210	1013	120	180	-26.9	231.7	OFF	240/15
				END	R 10				
154015	40	FL210	1013	121	220	-25.7	-30.1	OFF	235/10.
				Descent to	FL 170				
				START	RUN 11				
154442	41	FL 170	1013	120	250	-17.3	-32.8	OFF	225/12.
				END	RUN 11	/START P5			1100FT
161932	42	FL 170	1013	140	180	-16.0	-16.3	OFF	247/19
				Climb	P5 to 500 FPM				
163018	43	FL 060	1013	135	180	5.8	10.8	OFF	219/7
				END	P5				SS = 5
164004	44	500F	1022	145	180	15.8	14.8	OFF	196/7
				START	R 12				
164114	45	600F	1022	145		14.3	13.4	OFF	196/9
				END	RUN 12				
164253	46	600F	1022	145	180	14.5	13.8	OFF	198/9
				Climb to	Height				
				START	RUN 13				
174702	47	FL 070	1013	140	180	4.7	-0.9	OFF	292/9
				END	RUN 13				
175923	48	FL 070	1013	135	180	4.7	-4.5	OFF	302/7

Research Flight
 181645 ← → LAND SANTA MARIA

~~5 430 55W~~ ~~6 410 50W~~

VIDEO TAPE LOG

Flight No **A** 534

Project ACSOE

Date 07 04 97

Tape No A534 #2 User NERC

Retention Period 10 YRS

GMT	Tape Counter	Camera Position	Remarks
1430	0	FFC	Run 5 1000 ^{ft}
1442			Run 6 6000 ^{ft}
1454			Run 7 FL110
1513			Run 8 FL150
1526			Run 9 FL180
1536			Run 10 FL210
1544			Run 11 FL170
1641			Run 12 600 ^{ft}
1747			Run 13 FL070

VIDEO TAPE LOG

Flight No A 534.....

Project ALSOE.....

Date 070497.....

Tape No A534 #1.....

User NERC.....

Retention Period 10 YRS.....

GMT	Tape Counter	Camera Position	Remarks
1130	0	F/C	Run 2-1 FL200.
1305			Run 2-2 FL200
1327			PROF 1 FL200 - FL220.
1332			PROF 2 FL220 - FL260.
1342			PROF 3 FL260 - 50 RC.
1414			Run 4.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. A534

Date: 7/4/97

Operator: MF

Page 3 of 4

G.M.T.	PCASP			FSSP			2D-C			HVPS/2D-P			REMARKS
	DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Conc/cc	Max Size	Ref	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m ³	Max Size	Habit	
144500	80	0.09	0.4	0.4	5								
144700	85	0.09	0.4	0.4	5								
144900	85	0.09	0.3	0.3	5								
145100	85	0.09	0.3	0.3	5								
145300	80	0.09	0.9	0.9	5								
145444													
145781													end of Run Start Run 7 @ FL10
150000	156	0.08	0.07	0.07	5								
150200	126	0.08	0.06	0.06	5								
150400	90	0.08	0.04	0.04	5								
150724													
151331													end of Run Start Run 8 @ FL150
151400	15	0.08											
151600	60	0.08											
151800	100	0.08											
152000	100	0.08											
152100	90	0.08											
152230													
152630	40	0.08											end of Run Start Run 9 @ FL150
152700	35	0.08	0.03	0.03	5								
152900	40	0.09											
153100	35	0.09											
153300	23	0.08											
153326													
153625													end of Run Start Run 10 @ FL210
153700	86	0.09	0.06	0.06	5								
153900	30	0.09	0.03	0.03	5								
154016													
154142													end of Run Start Run 11 @ FL170
154500	60	0.09	0.02	0.02	5								
155000	15	0.09	0.04	0.04	5								
155200	10	0.11											
160000	16	0.11	0.04	0.04	5								
160500	14	0.11	0.05	0.05	5								
161000	25	0.15	80	80	20	9.4	60	820	8				
161500	20	0.12	10	10	45	7.9	17	880	8				

BAG Fillers Log

Flight No	Date	Operator
AS34.	7/4/97	Dave T

1/4
P.T.O.

Time	Bag No	Event	Height	Run	Comments
110840	87	110909	10000'	Run 2?	
12325	10009	112352	~15000'	probe	
13509	89	113550	20000'	Run 2	
144046	175	114526	20000'	"	
115350	86	115423	"		
20603	1006	12120640	"	"	
121545	61	121635	"	"	
122851	81	122530	"		
123508	238	123545	"		
124505	236	124545	"	"	
125500	237	125540	"	"	
130400	1008	130442	"	"	
31500	524	131536	"	"	
132515	525	132555	"	"	
133527	526	133617	Climb = 25000'	"	
134100	176	134148	FL 260	Run 3	
134240	239	134313	FL 260	"	
34305	115	134840	FL 260 ↓		
134706	111	134943	24700 ↓		
135070	113	135110	135110		
135140	110	135209	22000 ↓		
135240	112	135370	21000 ↓		
135335	1027	135420	21000 ↓		
135458	54	135574	21000 ↓		

BAG Fillers Log

Flight No	Date	Operator
ASB4	7/4/97	Dave

2/4

Time	Bag No	Event	Height	Run	Comments
135558	527	135615			
135646	256	135715			
135733	109	135759	16000b		
135840	258	135910	15000b		
135934	273	135957	14000b		
40020	272	140045			
40120	271	140145			
140220	259	140240			
140303	257	140340			
140356	275	140414			
140437	253	140453			
140518	254	140533			
140603	276	140626			
140645	274	140703			
140730	240	140747			
140817	277	140837			
140905	260	140923			
140958	255	141011			
141043	511	141056			
141110	535	141133			
141156	533	141217			
141250	537	141315			
141337	199	141352			
141436	37	141450			

BAG Fillers Log

Flight No	Date	Operator
AS34	7/4/97	Dave

3/4

P.T.O

Time	Bag No	Event	Height	Run	Comments
141517	133	141544	↓		
141604	530	141622	↓		
41655	532	141707	↓		
41731	534	141742	↓		
41808	528	141822			
41844	531	141856	50 ft		
42250	203	142309	100'	Run 4	
43412	204	143428	1000'	Run 5	
44400	207	144504	6000'	Run 6	
150228	221	150254	FL 110	Run 7	
151331	134	151424	FL 150	R 8	
152948	512	153020	FL 180	R 9	
153900	503	153841	FL 210	R 10	
155030	42	155100	FL 170	R 11	
160020	22	160050	FL 170	R 11	
160524	1021	160557	"	"	
161020	1013	161050	"	"	
161647	211	161720	"	"	
161933	222	162002	PS ↓	PS =	
162117	167	162155	"	"	
162258	210	162325	"	"	
162500	262	162538	"	"	
162702	212	162729	"	"	
162900	205	162921	"	"	

Instrument Log Sheet: 1202

Flight No: 534

Date: 2/4/92

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Campaign: ASOS/ASOS

Operator(s): PO

Time (GMT)	Altitude	Run	Zero / Cal	Comments
08:10				Power Sol ^s / Power Up Instrument
09:				Power On
				Recheck Instrument, Lamp etc
08:16	gnd	start up	Zero On	New Sol ^s .
08:34			Cal	HvA 128 HvB 121 30 Range mVts A _{max} 600 B _{max} 600 D ₅₀ A 238 B 238
			Cal th	A 243 B 243 (630 631)
08:43			Zero On	
09:04			Zero off	Zero OK & stable
09:103			Zero on	
09:33(1)			Zero off	
09:552				adjust zero to 030VdsA/B
				Take off.
10:2358				Power Check Start Descend Recheck Instrument
10:40			Zero off	
10:4938	3000'	SR1		Wts OK 1.64 Umin
10:4813	3000'	FR1		climb to 1000'
10:5730	10000'		Zero On	3.16 Umin
11:0030			Zero off	
11:1620	A			climbing to 20000'
11:3130	20000'			FR 1.12 Umin. @ 300kts
11:3140	20000'	SR2		TRANSIT TO TRANCREST
12:0010	"		Zero On	
12:1310			Zero off	Adjust to A 030 / 030 B
12:3025				in cloud with large particles of ICF (80 microns)
				Change in Nox / h ₀₁ O ₂ ≈ 12:32 gnd

Instrument Log Sheet: 1102

Flight No: 534

Date: July 12

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Campaign: RESOLVE (ARMS)

Operator(s): 2803

Time (GMT)	Altitude	Run	Zero / Cal	Comments
130510	20000	ER2.1	Zero	150 kts
130559	20000'	ER2.2		
130530			Zero off	150 kts Zero OK
				Adjusted Air B L (030)
132754	20000'	ER2.2		
132754	↑	SP22		Proble up to 1000'
	21000			TR 1.05 L/min
	22000			1.02
	23000			.96
	2400			.91
133730	25000			.85
	26000			.81
134057		EP2.1		Water layer seen
134057	26000'	SR3		
134808	↓	ER3		Feature w skin
134808		SP2		Proble to 50' 1000'/min
140642	66000'	↓		Change to 500'/min ascent
141140	4000'	↓		
141826	50'	EP3		
141909	110'	SR4		
142805	100'	ER4		
142505	↑	SP4.1		Climb to 1000'
143027	1000'	EP4.1		
143835	→	SR5	Zero On	
143335		-	Zero off	
143820	1000'	ER5		
1438	↑	SP4.2		Climb to 6000'
144239	6000'	EP4.2		
144239	→	SR6		
145442	↑	EP6		Climb to 11000'

Instrument Log Sheet: _____

Flight No: S34

Date: Jul 27

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Campaign: ASU02 | ASU20

Operator(s): JB

Time (GMT)	Altitude	Run	Zero / Cal	Comments
145442	↑	SP43		
145921	11000'	EP43		Midday profile reports
145921		SR7		good Turb Com. with O ₃
140910		ER7		
140910		SP44		climb to 15000'
151125	15030'	EP44		
151321	→	SR8		
151856		EP8	Zero On	
152230			Zero Off	
152231		EP8		
152514	↑	SP45		climbing to 15000'
152514		EP47		
152631	18000'	SR9		
152636	153331	ER9		
	↑	SP45		climbing to 20000'
153646	21000'	EP68		Boag collected @
153646		SR10		
154015	21000	ER10		TR 1.12 L/min
	↓			Descending to 17000'
154441	19000'	SR11		310 lbs Heady to Santa Monica
1607			Zero In	
1611			Zero Off	
161932	17000'	ER11		Descent in long holder
161932	↓	SP5		Down to 50' 1000'/min
		EP		
163016				Chase to 500'/min descent
164009	50'	EP5		
164419	600'	SR12		
164256	.	ER12		
	↑			climbing to Transh
	↑			

NOxy Instrument Pre-Flight Log Sheet

Flight No: AS34

Date: 7/4/97

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Campaign: ACOE/AZORES

Operator(s): TG SB AD

Time (GMT)	SEQ.	NO (cps)	NO2 (cps)	NOy 1 (cps)	NOy 2 (cps)	Comments
0630						Pumps started OK.
						GND ZERO AIR LEAK CHECKED AND FIXED
0645						CANS TO 600
0706						NB: BOTH R.V. TEMPS ARE EQUIVALENT. DEVIATE AFTER SWITCH ON.
0712						COUNTS LOOK - SAME AS PRE-FLIGHT ON 5.4.97 FOR EQ TIME
"		1145	1110	9426	5735	←
0714.						PROTOLYSIS LAMP 'ON' WATER WARMING IN FILTER.
0714						NB - CO CYLINDER LOW PRESSURE - 400psi
0721						COOLER 'ON'
0721						CO FLOWS HAD NOT BEEN SWITCHED 'ON' - 'BLIP' ON NOy's.
0755						POWER TRIPPED!
0809						POWER RESTART - CANS TO 300°C
0830						O3 HV ON NOXY RESTART COMPLETE
0844	ZERO			838	751	not sequenced (on NOy's)
0847	ZERO	488				not sequenced (on NO)
0849	ZERO					(on NO2)
0856	ZERO	465 485	1572	761	726	} manual artifact subtle off
	FLWS	545	1958	1411	1923	
						NO = 80 cps
						artifacts NO2 = 386 cps
						NOy1 = 650 cps
						NOy2 = 1197 cps
0915	CAL					GPT ON (NO2, NOy1, NOy2)
						↳ check flow log the sequenced cal (for NO2 conversion) should be
0925	→					pb w/ NO, NO2 & NOy1 cal very noisy although NO is not on calibration.
						↳ check flows on TOROR in diagnostic.
						↳ possible inlet contamination
0937	CM off					(NO2 cal) on NO2 / NOy1 / NOy2
					1768	8 min
					34279	4 1/2 min
1006						pb w/ contamination on inlet

Note: All times logged as GMT

Delivery Gases (Gnd-A/C) Change Over Time: _____

Power Change Over Time: _____

Can Flush On: _____

NOxy Instrument Pre-Flight Log Sheet

Flight No: AS 34

Date: 7/4/97

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Campaign: ACSDE/THOR

Operator(s): TGSB

Time (GMT)	SEQ.	NO (cps)	NO2 (cps)	NOy 1 (cps)	NOy 2 (cps)	Comments
1009	TIM					topping up sniffers w dry ice
1014	ZERO	735				all leads pl ⁽²⁾ on NO ₂
1044	MEAS	985				NO ₂ & NO ₂
						↳ ~30ppt of NO detected
	NB					can smell GND purifier unit exhaust in cabin!
1018	O ₂ HV OFF					
1021	ACQUISITION OFF					
1033	ARTIF. ON					before t/o sequenced

Note: All times logged as GMT

Delivery Gases (Gnd-A/C) Change Over Time: N/A

Power Change Over Time: ~1025

Can Flush On: NOT ON

NOxy Instrument In-Flight Log Sheet

Flight No: A534 Date: 7/4/97 Page: 1/4
 Campaign: ACSOE / AOROS Operator(s): SB / TG / KD
 Take-Off Time: 10:37 Can Flush Off: N/A

Note: Enter Sequence (SEQ.) as Calib, Zero, Artifact

Time (GMT)	Altitude	SEQ.	NO (cps)	NO2 (cps)	NOy 1 (cps)	NOy 2 (cps)	Comments	Run
1039	pb w	NOys	MEAS	on	ARTIF.		(due to +10) clouds	
	NOxy	clock	8 sec	slower	(from	DRS)		
104142	3000							SR1
104813								ER1
1048	end of	ARTIFACT			NOxy	on	AMBIENT MEAS	
1055	10000	CAL	—	1500	—	3500	sequenced CAL } NO2	
		ZERO	—	1375	—	529		
		CAL	44084	64731	54735	39704		
1105		ZERO	362	1265	708	489		Z
1111	NOxy	output	on	DRS	→	new zero values -		
1117	NO2	Φ	all	press.	1285	ton		
1117	starting	climbing	@	20000'	→	NOy 1 shows sharp decrease in signal which matches press. cabin change (cabin press. drops)		
	20000	increasing	speed to					
113140	20000	ZERO	371	4263	527	406	sequenced	SR2
114800	20000	ZERO	386	1157	489	376	sequenced	
115000		new zero values	led	into	DRS			
1204	20000	ZERO	335	1059	486	350	sequenced → repositioned to reposition way 15 min each way	
1218	20000	ZERO						
1221	→	80 cub offset (10 pptv)	led	in	NO	output to DRS		
1230	800	particles of ice	0.65					
123130	20000	ZERO					sequenced	
124940	20000	ZERO	328	1125	468	308	sequenced	
1251	all	DRS	output	updated	to	new zero values - NB NO output still offset @ +10 pptv		
1302	20000	ZERO	328	1067	443	294	sequenced	
130501	9000	deceleration	@	180	km/h			ER2 SR2

Note: All times logged as GMT

$$\text{ppt NO} = \frac{\text{act.} - \text{off}}{8}$$

NOxy Instrument In-Flight Log Sheet

Flight No: A534 Date: 7/4/97 Page: 21-1
 Campaign: ACSOE/AZORES Operator(s): TG/SD/KD
 Take-Off Time: 1037 Can Flush Off: N/A

Note: Enter Sequence (SEQ.) as Calib, Zero, Artifact

Time (GMT)	Altitude	SEQ.	NO (cps)	NO2 (cps)	NOy 1 (cps)	NOy 2 (cps)	Comments	Run	
1306	20000	CAZ	—	13899	—	33941	Midflight cal	} NO ₂ cal	
		ZERO	—	1148	493	280			
		CAF	43459	44712	45774	36496			} NO ₂ cal
1317		ZERO	347	1112	576	282	←		
1319			all zero values fed in conversions for DES outputs.						
132033	20000 ↑						ER2.2 SP2		
133701	22000 ↑								
1333		NO ₂	φ bar cell Press @			266 torr	Amb. Press.		
1333	23000					259 torr			
1335	23500					249 torr	403 mb		
1337	25000					227 torr	375 mb		
1338			→ A/C cleaning →			Noisy NOys			
1340	25900					205 torr	-37.8°C		
1340	25900					360 mb			
134057	26000							EP2	
134300	26000							SR3	
1348	26000	ZERO	434	1310	565	338			
134809							SP2	ER3	
	22000						NO ₂ cell φ Press @ 273 torr		
							NO ₂ φ cell Reprogramming OK		
1352							Press OK, slight overshoot.		
141836	50' ↑							EP3	
141810	100'							SR4	
142804	100' ↑						ER4	SP4.1	
143028	1000'						EP4.1	SR5	
143053	1000	ZERO	226	928	399	207			
1433			new zero values fed in conversions for DES outputs						
143820	1000 ↑							ER5/SP4.2	
144238	6000							EP4.2 SR6	
1452	6000	ZERO	236	1003	381	224	sequenced.		

Note: All times logged as GMT

NOxy Instrument In-Flight Log Sheet

Flight No: A534 Date: 7/19/97 Page: 31
 Campaign: AGOE/AFORS Operator(s): TO/SBIKD
 Take-Off Time: 1037 Can Flush Off: NA

Note: Enter Sequence (SEQ.) as Calib, Zero, Artifact

Time (GMT)	Altitude	SEQ.	NO (cps)	NO2 (cps)	NOy 1 (cps)	NOy 2 (cps)	Comments	Run
145442	↑						ER6/SP4.3	
145921	10000						EP4.3/SR7	
1501	→	engine resynchronization						
150736	10000↑						ER7/SP4.4	
151178	15000						EP4.4/ SR8	H2O spike @ 200.
151321	15000						SR8	
1519	15000	ZERO	341	1219	505	307	Zero sequenced	
152231	15000↑						ER8/SP4.5	
1525	18000						EP4.5/ SR9	
152631							SR9	
DON'T KNOW WHEN FAN BROKE DOWN		400 Hz cooling fan failure						
		higher loads due to oxidizer						
1533	18000	O3 C1	= 95	O3 tube temp. @ 62°C				
		O3 C2	= 24	O3 tube temp. 62°C				
153331	18000							
1535		cooling O3 tube to external fan/O3 Tube Temp. 50°C						
153640	21000						EP4.6	
							SR10	
1539							O3 tube temp. @ 44°C	
154015	21000						ER10	
154442	17000						SR11	
1554	17000	280 pts transmit back to S. Marie.						
1556	17000	ZERO	315	1160	418	290	sequenced.	
		NOy	O3 tube temp. @ 35°C					
		{ O3 C1	= 55					
		{ O3 C2	= 2.4					
<u>NS</u> : noisy NO2 signal probably due to moving cables when installing external fan								

Note: All times logged as GMT

NOxy Instrument In-Flight Log Sheet

Flight No: A534 Date: 7/4/97 Page: 4/14
 Campaign: ACCOSTAR0107 Operator(s): TG/LSB/KD
 Take-Off Time: 037 Can Flush Off: N/A

Note: Enter Sequence (SEQ.) as Calib, Zero, Artifact

Time (GMT)	Altitude	SEQ.	NO (cps)	NO2 (cps)	NOy 1 (cps)	NOy 2 (cps)	Comments	Run
1615	17000	slowing down to				180	lbs	
1617	17000	ZERO	515	1112	484	259	sequenced O ₂ tube temp = 32°C (snopk?)	
161932	17000						ER11	
1622		new zero values fed in conversion for DRS					SP5	
1635		new NO zero fed in conversion - (235)						
1640	6000	ZERO	234	917	402	211	sequence EPS/SR12	
164203	6000						ER12	
1643		new zero values fed in conversion for DRS						
1655	17000	A/C speeding up @ 280 lbs to final thrust						
1658	17000	ZERO	320	1105	460	295	} sequenced	
1714	21000	ZERO	351	1186	494	293		
1726		Last zero values fed in conversion for DRS						
1735		descending / approaching					Arabs	
1742	17000	ZERO	276	1134	458	253	sequenced.	
1744	↓ 7000	descending						
1747	7000	cal					sequenced	
174702	7000	cal	—	14081	12052	3181	} SR13 } NO ₂ cal } NO cal	
		∅	—	1025	447	225		
		cal	4381	4127	4517	4540		
		∅	255	977	495	212		
1758	7000	ARTIF. on					ZA values on manual override. NO _y on ZA	
175923	7000						end of R13	
1813		O ₂ HV off						
		LANDING TIME = 1817						

Note: All times logged as GMT

Formaldehyde Instrument Log Sheet

 Flight No: A53B

 Date: 7/6/97

 Page: 1 / 6

 Campaign: ALSOZ Azores Operator(s): _____

 Air Sampling Rate: 1.5L Peristaltic Pump Speed: 3 (rpm)

 PMT Sensitivity: 30 Calib Factor: _____ (V to ppt) _____ drs Bits = 1V

 Approx Lag Time: 8:30 fs React Coil Temp: 90°C

 @ 1.5m = 10.6 PPL / mU
 @ 1.5 = 7.5

Time (GMT)	Zero/Amb	Inst. Output (V)	Other Info/Remarks e.g. Altitude, lamp output, sampling rate changes etc.
9:32:15	Z	0.76	slight de bubbling prob.
09:48:20	Z	0.74	
10:04:55	Z	0.70	Started Zero, Lamp = 713 Power ok. 0.7
10:05:40	Z	0.85	~ 1.8 ppbv on Brian's laptop
10:08:30	Z		- de bubbling problem
10:10:20	Z		Applied correction - last 30
10:15:20	Z		secs - next 30 secs uncorrected
10:15:28	Z		Air Sample pipe closed
10:20:38	Z	1.05	Start Run (1) @ 3000'
10:43:47	A	1.02	tuned off 300 - Didn't go down - zero nominally 0.70 V.
10:48:15			Start Run (1) → 3000 - end Run (1)
			Point (1) start - 3000 → 1000'
			or
10:56:17	A	0.66	10000' 180 kts(?) (Sample = 1.15 SLM) debubbler a bit low
10:57:43	Z	0.66	STARTED ZERO (Flow = 1.06L)
11:08:02	A	0.76	- Zero went up - didn't come down - Don't know why. - Flows look ok. END ZERO
11:08:30			Climb + accel rate = WARP + 20000
11:22:30	A	0.60	15500, Flow = 0.93 SLM Must do ground zero at 20000
11:31:40	A	0.61	Start Run (2) @ 20000 Flow = 0.77 m ³ / min - one or two bubbles (Sharp large mag peaks) now clear!

Formaldehyde Instrument Log Sheet

Flight No: A53L Date: _____ Page: 2/6
 Campaign: Acsoe Azores fl Operator(s): MLH
 Air Sampling Rate: 0.77020 Peristaltic Pump Speed: _____ (rpm)
 PMT Sensitivity: @ 20000 Calib Factor: _____ (V to ppt) _____ drs Bits = 1V
 Approx Lag Time: _____ React Coil Temp: _____

Time (GMT)	Zero/Amb	Inst. Output (V)	Other Info/Remarks e.g. Altitude, lamp output, sampling rate changes etc.
11:43:30			Bubble - spike on data ignore.
12:01:37	Zero	0.60	Start long zero: Flow = 0.64 lmp = 7.07 μ V ~ 0.2 0.2 ppbv on Brains laptop
12:05:30			few bubbles getting through System. debubbler at its limit
12:17:07	Zero	0.63	- Zero settling down now etc going up considerably at the beginning - reason unknown but data for ~ 12:05 $\rightarrow$ 12:17 is not valid zero
12:25:00	Zero	0.60	Baseline is <u>(poor)</u> for fast zero min. at zero noise $\approx$ 200+ ppt. $\therefore$ det lim $\approx$ 400 ppt! at the moment Zero here 0.2: 0.06 ppbv on brains PC.
			Prob. Bad liquid/degenerate flow PROBLEMS AT THESE ALTITUDES
12:42:00	Zero	0.57	Zero mainly 0.61/60
12:47:16	A	0.59	Start measure - end zero
12:54:30	A	0.62	0.3 on Brains PC + falling - may be valve artefact / leak with valve port for amb sample. - <u>check</u> <u>@ uen</u>

Brains PC has low = 0.0075 ppbv
 on scaling factor - city correct @ 1.5

Formaldehyde Instrument Log Sheet

 Flight No: A536

 Date: 7/4/97 Page: 3 / 6

Campaign: _____ Operator(s): _____

Air Sampling Rate: _____ Peristaltic Pump Speed: _____ (rpm)

PMT Sensitivity: _____ Calib Factor: _____ (V to ppt) _____ drs Bits = 1V

Approx Lag Time: _____ React Coil Temp: _____

Time (GMT)	Zero/Amb	Inst. Output (V)	Other Info/Remarks e.g. Altitude, lamp output, sampling rate changes etc.
131740	A	0.58	Zero ^{was} is v. noisy in → 300 ppt - from flow prob at altitude
132733	A		START PROFILE (1) to 26000 @ 500' / min end Run (2-2)
132750	A	0.58	flow = 0.6
133120			inlet (1) intercept alt 220
133201	A	0.57	restart inlet (1), flow = 0.67
1334	A	0.	de bubble start flows start to break down - quite a few spikes due to bubbles
			in flow = 0.55 SLM
134057			end profile (1) at 26000' start Run (3)
134809			End Run (3) start Profile (2) in 26000'
135210	A		De bubble started again ~ 21500'
135550	A	0.55	flow = 0.7
14013	A	0.56	flow = 1.0
140355	A		inlet 9700
140601	A	0.57	flow # = 1.35 SLM
140616	A	0.57	FL 6600
141308	A	0.57/8	~ FL 3000 flow = 1.55 SLM
141836			End P(3) @ 150'
141910	A	0.60	Start R(4) @ 100' 180 ppt
142530	A	0.61	
142805	A	0.61	End R(4) start P(4) for 100'
143028	A	0.	end P(4) start R(5)
			Run (5) = No data because of leak

Back online 14:38:39.

Formaldehyde Instrument Log Sheet

Flight No: A534

Date: 7/14/97

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Campaign: ACS06 A3000 Operator(s): _____

Air Sampling Rate: _____ Peristaltic Pump Speed: _____ (rpm)

PMT Sensitivity: _____ Calib Factor: _____ (V to ppt) _____ drs Bits = 1V

Approx Lag Time: _____ React Coil Temp: _____

Time (GMT)	Zero/Amb	Inst. Output (V)	Other Info/Remarks e.g. Altitude, lamp output, sampling rate changes etc.
16:4530	A	—	Climb to fl 170 @ WARP
16:4801	A	0.93	bubble problems! - stopped output from cell to build up buffer in debubbler - next few mins could be ^{invaluable} useful
17:0034	A	0.66	Flow = 0.81 SLM, Lamp = 711 Co. react Temp = 92°C
17:0606	A	0.645	1400 ftd during climb
17:1333	Z	0.65	STARTED ZERO, sample rate = 0.6 SLM
17:1809	Z		debubbler getting close to limit (works better @ higher sample rate.)
17:2420	Z	0.61	
17:2858	A	0.61	ended zero - (20 bit noise)
17:3645	A		Descending to _____, current = 13000' flow = 0.99
17:4220	Z	0.64	start zero @ 7000'
17:4702			SR (18) @ FLO70
17:5927	AZ	0.61	ER (16) @
18:0400	Z	—	corrected debubble buffer 2000' went up (back Mustang) Hopefully come down before landing END FLIGHT

Formaldehyde Instrument Log Sheet

 Flight No: A 534

 Date: 7/12/97

 Page: 4 / 6

Campaign: _____ Operator(s): _____

Air Sampling Rate: _____ Peristaltic Pump Speed: _____ (rpm)

PMT Sensitivity: _____ Calib Factor: _____ (V to ppt) _____ drs Bits = 1V

Approx Lag Time: _____ React Coil Temp: _____

Time (GMT)	Zero/Amb	Inst. Output (V)	Other Info/Remarks e.g. Altitude, lamp output, sampling rate changes etc.
14:38:20	A		end R(5)
14:42:39	A		debubbler taking too much liquid! end P 4.2 start Run (6)
14:54:42	A		- Debubbler FF was not working changed debubbler ⇒ 0/0 (slow)
14:59:31	A	0.88	start P 4.3 end Run (6) end P 4.3 start Run (7) Flow = 1.11 SLM
15:07:36	A	0.65	Signal prob high due to Pump tube change over end P 4.3 R (7) start P (8) (4)
15:11:28			Sample Rate = 0.87 end P 4.4 @ Fl 150
15:13:21	A		Start P (8)
15:22:44			end H (8) start P (4) (3)
15:25:14	A		end P 4.5, SR (9) @ 18000
15:26:31			SR (9) @ Fl 180
15:31:00	A	0.63	Flow = 0.78 SLM
15:33:31			FR9 S P 4.6 - new debubbler almost at limit
15:37:46	A	0.63	SR 10 P 4.6 @ Fl 210
15:40:15	A		end R 10
15:44:41	A	0.64	decending to fl 170 SR 11 Fl 170, Corp Speed. Flow = 0.82 SLM
15:46:44	Z	0.63	Started Zero. Fl = 0.75 - debubbler struggling - occasional bubbles → detritus

Formaldehyde Instrument Log Sheet

 Flight No: A534

 Date: 7/4/77

 Page: 516

Campaign: _____ Operator(s): _____

Air Sampling Rate: _____ Peristaltic Pump Speed: _____ (rpm)

PMT Sensitivity: _____ Calib Factor: _____ (V to ppt) _____ drs Bits = 1V

Approx Lag Time: _____ React Coil Temp: _____

Time (GMT)	Zero/Amb	Inst. Output (V)	Other Info/Remarks e.g. Altitude, lamp output, sampling rate changes etc.
155034	Z	0.62	Zero is noisy + doesn't go down! :- Prob not working
160100	A		Turn off BWD zero
160100	A	0.62	Appears instrument <u>not</u> working at least not at these sample flows + pressures.
161810	A	0.65 0.82	(21200 mu sig ~ 2000 pptV?)
		↑ reading Air flow!	Sig. on bridge PC only small increment in 155034 → may not have been 0.62 but 0.22 or near! (reading error?)
1619:32	A	0.65 0.52	ER(11) SR(5) FL170
162720	A	0.65	- No bubbler now falling - bubble going to detector.
163018		0.72	Chng rate descent @ 1060 to 500' / min I am now seeing sig. level of HCHO
163716	A	0.83	ALT = 2700' approx ≈ 1.4 pptV HCHO (V. high)
164009			EP(3) @ 50' & SR(6)
164119			SR(12) 600'
164223	A	0.80	ER(13) dt bubbler still causing problems.

A534, 7th April, 1997
 ACSOE
 North West of Santa Maria FIR.

Start time	End time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
103605					Take off from Santa Maria
103938	104813	R1	3000'	315°	Instrument warm up run
113140	130501	R2.1	FL200	320°	220kts IAS
130559	132733	R2.2	FL200	320°	180kts IAS
132733	133111	P1	FL200- FL220	320°	
133201	134057	P2	FL220- FL260	045°	
134057	134809	R3	FL260	240°	
134809	141838	P3	FL260- 50 ft	045°	1000fpm, 500fpm from FL060
141910	142805	R4	100'	050°	
142805	143028	P4.1	100'- 1000'	230°	500fpm
143028	143820	R5	1000'	230°	
143820	144239	P4.2	1000'- 6000'	230°	1500fpm
144239	145442	R6	6000'	230°	
145442	145921	P4.3	6000'- FL110	060°	1500fpm
145921	150736	R7	FL110	060°	
150736	151128	P4.4	FL110- FL150	045°	1500fpm
151321	152231	R8	FL150	230°	
152231	152507	P4.5	FL150- FL180	230°	1500fpm
152631	153331	R9	FL180	055°	
153331	153646	P4.6	FL180- FL210	120°	1000fpm
153646	154015	R10	FL210	120°	
154442	161932	R11	FL170	140°	245kts IAS
161932	164009	P5	FL170- 50 ft	140°	1000fpm, 500fpm from FL060
164119	164253	R12	600'	145°	
174702	175923	R13	FL070	140°	
181645					Land at Santa Maria. 36°58.30'N 025°09.85'W

FLIGHT LEADER'S INSTRUMENT STATUS REPORT

FLIGHT NO: 534

DATE: 07 104 197

MRF

INSTRUMENT	FITTED	OPERATED	COMMENTS
NAVIGATION: GPS OMEGA INU RADALT	/ / / /		
THERMOMETERS: DI TEMP NDI TEMP ICTP HEIMANN HYGROMETERS: GEN. EASTERN TWC FWVS J/W EXP. PITOT HEAD: STATIC PRESS. PITOT PRESS. GUST VANES	/ / / / / / / / / / / / / /		
RADIOMETERS: UPPER CLEAR UPPER RED UPPER SILICON LOWER CLEAR LOWER RED LOWER SILICON MARSS SAFIRE DEIMOS ARIES	/ / 3NO2 / / 3NO2 X X X X		
CHEMISTRY: OZONE ECGC NOX	/ / /		
OTHERS: CCN CLOUD PHYSICS CABIN PRESS NEPHELOMETER PSAP	X / / X X		

A534 07-APR-97 18:08:12 048 Ω 37.18 -25.80 RV P

HDG deg T 119.	SPR mb 789.	PHGT kft 6.8	TAS knots 283.	TAT C 7.9	DEW C -13.6	WIND deg m/s 274/9
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OZONE MR 0.00 NOXY NOY 35.71

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	RADAR	AREA	TRAV				

A534 07-APR-97 18:09:57 048 37.11 -25.64 FC P

HDG deg 118.	SPR mb 789.	PHST kft 6.8	TAS knts 283.	TAT C 7.0	DEW C -8.2	WIND deg m/s 288/9
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	

Chart11

Descent 1: A534

A534

A534 desc2

Descent 2 A534

300MB

HEIGHT DM.

T + 24

GMAIN

8 / 4 / 97

IUES

VI OUZ

7 / 4 / 97

MUN

IPHDE30 EGRR 0000Z

CHART 27

LAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 509 SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03:39.46

500-1000MB
500MB

THICKNESS DM.
HEIGHT DM.

T+0

GRAIN

7/4/97

VT 00Z MON

7/4/97

T 00Z MON

ILAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03.45.47

CHART 13

PHEASO EGRR 0000Z

I 00Z MON 7/ 4/97 VI 00Z TUES 8/ 4/97 CMAIN T + 24

--- THICKNESS DM.
500-1000MB
500MB

STEREOPHOTOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03:45:58

CHART 13

PHEE50 EGRR 0000Z

07 APR '97 04:36

ASXX EGRR MSLP ANALYSIS DT 0000 UTC 07 APR 1997

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Original scale 1:20m

Prepared by the Cartographic Section, METD/LDC, as shown. METD/LDC is responsible for the content of this chart. METD/LDC is not responsible for the content of this chart.

FSXX EGRR 24H MSLP FORECAST VT 0800 UTC 08 APR 1997

Polar Stereographic Projection. Standard Parallel 60°N. Original scale 1:20m

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
5 — —	Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log
10 3 2 / 2	Flight Leader pre-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight log Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)
4 1 6	SAFIRE log BAGS CCN log BOTTLES MARSS log PAN-GC TRACE DEIMOS log Chemistry log
4	Particulate / Filter boom Operator's log 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)
1 — — — — —	Instrument status forms RTD prints Raw data plots Weather charts Satellite pictures GPS track

A534 07-APR-97 R3 FL260 From 134057-134809 Plotled 9-Jun-1997 11:37

A534 07-APR-97 R3 FL260 From 134057-134809 Plotted 9-gunn-1997 11:37

Flight A534

From 12Z 2/ 4/1997 to 18Z 7/ 4/1997

Arrows every 24 hrs

A534 07-APR-97

P1-2 FL200-FL260(132733-134057) + P3 FL260-50'(134809-141838)

A534 07-APR-97

P4 100'-FL210(142805-153646) + P5 FL170-50'(161932-164009)

A534 07-APR-97 R2.1 FL200 220kts IAS From 113140-130501 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 13:11

A534 07-APR-97 R2.1 FL200 220kts IAS From 113140-130501 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 13:11

A534 07-APR-97 R2.1 FL200 220kts IAS From 113140-130501 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 14:21

A534 07-APR-97 R2.1 FL200 220kts IAS From 113140-130501 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 14:22

A534 07-APR-97 R2.1 FL200 220kts IAS From 113140-130501 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 13:11

A534 07-APR-97 R2.1 FL200 220kts IAS From 113140-130501 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 13:11

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 5602
Mean 465.598
Standard dev 0.337699
Max value 467.209
Min value 464.854

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 5602
Mean 44.5091
Standard dev 15.3506
Max value 77.3406
Min value 27.6287

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 5602
Mean 6096.45
Standard dev 5.27597
Max value 6108.08
Min value 6071.31

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 5602
Mean 5.16547
Standard dev 4.59076
Max value 12.0924
Min value -5.54227

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 5602
Mean 15.4881
Standard dev 2.80090
Max value 20.6356
Min value 9.95726

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 249.548

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 5602
Mean 253.312
Standard dev 1.26539
Max value 255.748
Min value 249.680

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)
No of obs 5602
Mean 12.1355
Standard dev 1.52784
Max value 17.3380
Min value 7.55207

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 5602
Mean 40.3701
Standard dev 1.23256
Max value 42.6359
Min value 38.4837

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 5602
Mean 13.8510
Standard dev 2.84989
Max value 19.4342
Min value 8.44896

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 5602
Mean 154.420
Standard dev 3.50957
Max value 158.569
Min value 126.607

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 5602
Mean 251.941
Standard dev 1.65357
Max value 255.151
Min value 247.500

PEROXIDE (PPB)
No of obs 5602
Mean 0.311012
Standard dev 6.035794e-02
Max value 0.496000
Min value 1.600000e-02

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 5602
Mean -32.4039
Standard dev 2.26426
Max value -28.4999
Min value -36.3575

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 5602
Mean 0.359314
Standard dev 0.314979
Max value 1.47183
Min value -1.40249

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 304.655

A534 07-APR-97 R2.2 FL200 180kts IAS From 130559-132733 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 11:33

A534 07-APR-97 R2.2 FL200 180kts IAS From 130559-132733 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 11:33

A534 07-APR-97 R2.2 FL200 180kts IAS From 130559-132733 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 14:26

A534 07-APR-97 R2.2 FL200 180kts IAS From 130559-132733 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 14:26

A534 07-APR-97 R2.2 FL200 180kts IAS From 130559-132733 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 11:33

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 1295
 Mean 464.781
 Standard dev 0.409982
 Max value 466.787
 Min value 463.465

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 1295
 Mean 248.453
 Standard dev 0.623392
 Max value 249.770
 Min value 247.518

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 1295
 Mean 241.429
 Standard dev 5.88119
 Max value 249.728
 Min value 226.223

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 1295
 Mean 56.1181
 Standard dev 1.12756
 Max value 59.1175
 Min value 52.7929

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)
 No of obs 1295
 Mean 12.1282
 Standard dev 0.918542
 Max value 13.8301
 Min value 9.00830

PEROXIDE (PPB)
 No of obs 1295
 Mean 0.230456
 Standard dev 9.485971e-02
 Max value 0.416000
 Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 1295
 Mean 6109.22
 Standard dev 6.40780
 Max value 6129.83
 Min value 6077.89

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1295
 Mean 43.1218
 Standard dev 0.248432
 Max value 43.5447
 Min value 42.6829

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1295
 Mean -37.2149
 Standard dev 0.459619
 Max value -36.4329
 Min value -38.0149

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1295
 Mean 11.2972
 Standard dev 1.52978
 Max value 13.3360
 Min value 7.55756

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1295
 Mean 8.84525
 Standard dev 1.15355
 Max value 11.0192
 Min value 6.25579

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1295
 Mean -0.106626
 Standard dev 0.196416
 Max value 0.451797
 Min value -0.757530

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 1295
 Mean 14.4528
 Standard dev 0.805992
 Max value 16.0156
 Min value 12.7486

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 218.060

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 1295
 Mean 124.926
 Standard dev 1.82380
 Max value 131.825
 Min value 119.718

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 306.640

A534 07-APR-97 P1-2 FL200-FL260 From 132733-134057 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 14:29

A534 07-APR-97 P1-2 FL200-FL260 From 132733-134057 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 14:28

A534 07-APR-97 P1-2 FL200-FL260 From 132733-134057 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 11:36

A534 07-APR-97 P1-2 FL200-FL260 From 132733-134057 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 11:36

A534 07-APR-97 P1-2 FL200-FL260 From 132733-134057 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 11:36

A534 07-APR-97 R3 FL260 From 134057-134809 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 14:30

A534 07-APR-97 R3 FL260 From 134057 - 134809 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 14:31

A534 07-APR-97 R3 FL260 From 134057-134809 Potted 9-Jun-1997 11:37

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 433
 Mean 359.628
 Standard dev 0.160742
 Max value 360.155
 Min value 359.384

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 433
 Mean 235.579
 Standard dev 7.020634e-02
 Max value 235.716
 Min value 235.454

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 433
 Mean 225.823
 Standard dev 1.01894
 Max value 227.390
 Min value 223.232

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 433
 Mean 72.2544
 Standard dev 16.1449
 Max value 81.9734
 Min value 1.000000e-38

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)

No of obs 433
 Mean 12.4709
 Standard dev 1.098894e-02
 Max value 12.5373
 Min value 12.4440

PEROXIDE (PPB)

No of obs 433
 Mean 0.123529
 Standard dev 2.680173e-02
 Max value 0.176000
 Min value 3.199999e-02

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 433
 Mean 7929.69
 Standard dev 3.09520
 Max value 7934.39
 Min value 7919.54

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 433
 Mean 43.8977
 Standard dev 9.602854e-02
 Max value 44.0625
 Min value 43.7341

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 433
 Mean -38.0681
 Standard dev 0.113883
 Max value -37.8745
 Min value -38.2629

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 433
 Mean 17.6550
 Standard dev 0.434364
 Max value 18.7027
 Min value 16.8525

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 433
 Mean 26.6714
 Standard dev 0.424480
 Max value 27.7664
 Min value 25.5801

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 433
 Mean -0.422560
 Standard dev 0.179210
 Max value 0.588791
 Min value -0.961372

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 433
 Mean 31.9880
 Standard dev 0.446274
 Max value 33.0389
 Min value 30.7937

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 236.498

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 433
 Mean 142.009
 Standard dev 2.90899
 Max value 146.192
 Min value 136.267

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 220.525

A534 07-APR-97 P3 FL260-50' From 134809-141838 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 11:43

A534 07-APR-97 P3 FL260-50' From 134809-141838 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 11:44

A534 07-APR-97 P3 FL260-50' From 134809-141838 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 14:36

A534 07-APR-97 P3 FL260-50' From 134809-141838 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 14:36

A534 07-APR-97 P3 FL260-50' From 134809-141838 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 11:44

A534 07-APR-97 R4 100' From 141910-142805 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 11:45

A534 07-APR-97 R4 100' From 141910-142805 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 11:45

A534 07-APR-97 R4 100' From 141910-142805 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 14:39

A534 07-APR-97 R4 100' From 141910 - 142805 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 14:39

A534 07-APR-97 R4 100' From 141910-142805 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 11:46

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 536
 Mean 1013.63
 Standard dev 0.180603
 Max value 1014.08
 Min value 1013.13

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 536
 Mean 288.828
 Standard dev 3.699335e-02
 Max value 288.914
 Min value 288.742

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 536
 Mean 287.452
 Standard dev 0.109971
 Max value 287.686
 Min value 287.094

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 536
 Mean 41.2399
 Standard dev 1.31047
 Max value 46.1966
 Min value 38.3590

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)
 No of obs 536
 Mean 42.6116
 Standard dev 17.8812
 Max value 52.6893
 Min value 7.21488

PEROXIDE (PPB)
 No of obs 536
 Mean 0.168910
 Standard dev 2.344290e-02
 Max value 0.256000
 Min value 0.120000

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 536
 Mean 31.3446
 Standard dev 1.75336
 Max value 36.8186
 Min value 27.8977

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 536
 Mean 43.8093
 Standard dev 0.120717
 Max value 44.0167
 Min value 43.6000

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 536
 Mean -38.8060
 Standard dev 9.623051e-02
 Max value -38.6397
 Min value -38.9718

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 536
 Mean 6.45194
 Standard dev 0.407657
 Max value 7.70231
 Min value 5.38438

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 536
 Mean 3.11243
 Standard dev 0.260563
 Max value 3.96786
 Min value 2.35088

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 536
 Mean -5.846818e-02
 Standard dev 0.396690
 Max value 1.15986
 Min value -0.674057

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 536
 Mean 7.16793
 Standard dev 0.411768
 Max value 8.40839
 Min value 6.02982

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 205.753

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 536
 Mean 92.4742
 Standard dev 1.96867
 Max value 96.1003
 Min value 89.2932

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 30.0039

A534 07-APR-97 P4 100'-FL210 From 142805-153646 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 14:51

A534 07-APR-97 P4 100-FL210 From 142805-153646 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 14:51

A534 07-APR-97 P4 100'-FL210 From 142805-153646 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 11:56

A534 07-APR-97 P4 100'-FL210 From 142805-153646 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 11:56

A534 07-APR-97 P4 100'-FL210 From 142805-153646 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 11:56

A534 07-APR-97 R5 1000' From 143028-143820 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 11:58

A534 07-APR-97 R5 1000' From 143028 - 143820 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 11:58

A534 07-APR-97 R5 1000' From 143028 - 143820 Plotted 20 - Jun - 1997 14:54

A534 07-APR-97 R5 1000' From 143028-143820 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 14:54

A534 07-APR-97 R5 1000' From 143028-143820 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 11:58

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 471
 Mean 982.063
 Standard dev 0.317214
 Max value 982.856
 Min value 981.264

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 471
 Mean 286.475
 Standard dev 3.221316e-02
 Max value 286.589
 Min value 286.378

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 471
 Mean 285.960
 Standard dev 0.131180
 Max value 286.345
 Min value 285.513

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 471
 Mean 41.3717
 Standard dev 1.30907
 Max value 44.6977
 Min value 37.9200

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)

No of obs 471
 Mean 52.5675
 Standard dev 7.757561e-03
 Max value 52.5809
 Min value 52.5484

PEROXIDE (PPB)

No of obs 471
 Mean 0.128051
 Standard dev 6.139927e-02
 Max value 0.224000
 Min value 1.600000e-02

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 471
 Mean 307.047
 Standard dev 3.37504
 Max value 312.809
 Min value 299.056

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 471
 Mean 43.8429
 Standard dev 9.536801e-02
 Max value 44.0083
 Min value 43.6781

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 471
 Mean -38.6684
 Standard dev 6.668250e-02
 Max value -38.5519
 Min value -38.7839

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 471
 Mean 3.80238
 Standard dev 0.284421
 Max value 4.49295
 Min value 2.99531

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 471
 Mean 5.97364
 Standard dev 0.247846
 Max value 6.85246
 Min value 5.50070

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 471
 Mean -0.217501
 Standard dev 0.286662
 Max value 0.236671
 Min value -0.886276

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 471
 Mean 7.08605
 Standard dev 0.269234
 Max value 7.82833
 Min value 6.58471

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 237.522

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 471
 Mean 93.1005
 Standard dev 1.57865
 Max value 99.0842
 Min value 91.1367

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 206.950

A534 07-APR-97 R6 6000' From 144239-145442 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:00

A534 07-APR-97 R6 6000' From 144239-145442 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:00

A534 07-APR-97 R6 6000' From 144239-145442 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 14:57

A534 07-APR-97 R6 6000' From 144239 - 145442 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 14:57

A534 07-APR-97 R6 6000' From 144239-145442 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:00

A534 07-APR-97 R6 6000' From 144239-145442 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:00

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 722
Mean 816.553
Standard dev 0.233904
Max value 817.530
Min value 815.483

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 722
Mean 275.554
Standard dev 7.491280e-02
Max value 275.727
Min value 275.379

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 722
Mean 273.793
Standard dev 0.304999
Max value 274.595
Min value 273.234

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 722
Mean 47.7125
Standard dev 1.13314
Max value 50.7045
Min value 43.8444

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)

No of obs 722
Mean 53.0447
Standard dev 1.796989e-02
Max value 53.1011
Min value 52.8302

PEROXIDE (PPB)

No of obs 721
Mean 1.21978
Standard dev 0.739590
Max value 4.19200
Min value 0.288000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 722
Mean 1783.49
Standard dev 2.31923
Max value 1794.10
Min value 1773.81

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 722
Mean 43.1912
Standard dev 0.164454
Max value 43.4807
Min value 42.9088

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 722
Mean -38.8942
Standard dev 5.40044
Max value 105.986
Min value -39.2811

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 722
Mean 1.81110
Standard dev 3.20604
Max value 87.4094
Min value 0.616348

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 722
Mean 5.78559
Standard dev 8.05849
Max value 7.07436
Min value -210.065

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 722
Mean -0.732791
Standard dev 13.9733
Max value 0.720665
Min value -374.877

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 721
Mean 6.32844
Standard dev 0.416437
Max value 7.19811
Min value 5.23053

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 252.618

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 722
Mean 101.530
Standard dev 1.68377
Max value 108.397
Min value 99.5142

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 205.842

A534 07-APR-97 R7 FL110 From 145921-150736 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:02

A534 07-APR-97 R7 FL110 From 145921-150736 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:02

A534 07-APR-97 R7 FL110 From 145921-150736 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 14:59

A534 07-APR-97 R7 FL110 From 145921-150736 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 14:59

A534 07-APR-97 R7 FL110 From 145921-150736 Potted 9-Jun-1997 12:02

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 496
 Mean 670.670
 Standard dev 0.236993
 Max value 671.053
 Min value 669.307

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 496
 Mean 268.329
 Standard dev 7.000209e-02
 Max value 268.516
 Min value 268.206

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 496
 Mean 248.458
 Standard dev 0.882173
 Max value 250.004
 Min value 245.603

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 496
 Mean 56.9307
 Standard dev 0.850493
 Max value 59.1544
 Min value 54.0705

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)
 No of obs 496
 Mean 52.8508
 Standard dev 3.95466
 Max value 53.2203
 Min value 0.969524

PEROXIDE (PPB)
 No of obs 496
 Mean 0.567226
 Standard dev 5.041385e-02
 Max value 0.712000
 Min value 0.472000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 496
 Mean 3347.26
 Standard dev 2.75584
 Max value 3363.11
 Min value 3342.80

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 496
 Mean 43.1875
 Standard dev 1.94613
 Max value 43.4818
 Min value 1.178295e-02

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 496
 Mean -38.9387
 Standard dev 1.75736
 Max value 6.570916e-03
 Min value -39.2478

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 496
 Mean 8.65265
 Standard dev 0.941136
 Max value 9.53951
 Min value -10.7734

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 496
 Mean 5.93739
 Standard dev 0.525420
 Max value 13.8256
 Min value 4.09785

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 496
 Mean -0.372322
 Standard dev 1.08132
 Max value 0.742012
 Min value -9.32930

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 494
 Mean 10.5237
 Standard dev 0.408292
 Max value 11.2193
 Min value 9.66640

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 214.458

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 496
 Mean 109.411
 Standard dev 3.25787
 Max value 115.241
 Min value 104.181

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 39.8157

A534 07-APR-97 R8 FL150 From 151321-152231 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:03

A534 07-APR-97 R8 FL150 From 151321-152231 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:03

A534 07-APR-97 R8 FL150 From 151321-152231 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 15:01

A534 07-APR-97 R8 FL150 From 151321-152231 *Plotled 20-Jun-1997 15:01*

A534 07-APR-97 R8 FL150 From 151321-152231 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:03

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 551
 Mean 573.007
 Standard dev 0.233665
 Max value 573.624
 Min value 572.577

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 551
 Mean 260.082
 Standard dev 8.303533e-02
 Max value 260.255
 Min value 259.908

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 551
 Mean 236.837
 Standard dev 0.507004
 Max value 238.130
 Min value 236.014

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 551
 Mean 53.4295
 Standard dev 5.41293
 Max value 59.6796
 Min value 42.0123

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)
 No of obs 551
 Mean 53.6084
 Standard dev 6.471633e-03
 Max value 53.6430
 Min value 53.5997

PEROXIDE (PPB)
 No of obs 551
 Mean 0.309691
 Standard dev 5.021914e-02
 Max value 0.840000
 Min value 0.152000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 551
 Mean 4556.23
 Standard dev 3.08586
 Max value 4561.91
 Min value 4548.08

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 551
 Mean 43.4720
 Standard dev 0.131078
 Max value 43.6968
 Min value 43.2415

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 551
 Mean -38.7223
 Standard dev 0.103562
 Max value -38.5477
 Min value -38.9065

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 551
 Mean 7.73700
 Standard dev 0.660342
 Max value 8.88731
 Min value 6.58672

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 551
 Mean 7.79668
 Standard dev 0.746601
 Max value 8.75624
 Min value 6.22889

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 551
 Mean 0.159494
 Standard dev 0.365712
 Max value 0.804985
 Min value -1.26009

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 551
 Mean 11.0086
 Standard dev 0.673492
 Max value 12.2695
 Min value 9.74659

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 225.220

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 551
 Mean 116.461
 Standard dev 3.42826
 Max value 122.365
 Min value 111.919

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 209.850

A534 07-APR-97 R9 FL180 From 152631-153331 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:05

A534 07-APR-97 R9 FL180 From 152631-153331 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:05

A534 07-APR-97 R9 FL180 From 152631-153331 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 15:02

A534 07-APR-97 R9 FL180 From 152631-153331 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 15:02

A534 07-APR-97 R9 FL180 From 152631-153331 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:05

A534 07-APR-97 R9 FL180 From 152631-153331 *Plotted* 9-Jun-1997 12:05

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 421
Mean 507.656
Standard dev 0.110272
Max value 507.983
Min value 507.439

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 421
Mean 253.440
Standard dev 0.148605
Max value 253.718
Min value 253.166

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 421
Mean 238.227
Standard dev 3.01982
Max value 241.923
Min value 231.038

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 421
Mean 58.1608
Standard dev 2.70796
Max value 62.1946
Min value 50.9637

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)
No of obs 421
Mean 52.6589
Standard dev 5.65713
Max value 53.4588
Min value 11.2165

PEROXIDE (PPB)
No of obs 421
Mean 0.232589
Standard dev 2.788470e-02
Max value 0.320000
Min value 0.168000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 421
Mean 5462.13
Standard dev 1.60627
Max value 5465.29
Min value 5457.37

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 421
Mean 43.3200
Standard dev 0.119369
Max value 43.5265
Min value 43.1144

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 421
Mean -38.7137
Standard dev 0.113818
Max value -38.5173
Min value -38.9117

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 421
Mean 8.10945
Standard dev 0.307280
Max value 8.86018
Min value 7.44547

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 421
Mean 8.12933
Standard dev 0.326102
Max value 9.03407
Min value 7.20910

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 421
Mean -0.147765
Standard dev 0.639815
Max value 0.636673
Min value -1.46236

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 421
Mean 11.4886
Standard dev 0.250744
Max value 12.0845
Min value 10.9933

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 225.070

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 421
Mean 121.502
Standard dev 0.395644
Max value 122.739
Min value 120.729

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 34.9534

A534 07-APR-97 R10 FL210 From 153646-154015 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:06

A534 07-APR-97 R10 FL210 From 153646-154015 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:06

A534 07-APR-97 R10 FL210 From 153646-154015 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 15:04

A534 07-APR-97 R10 FL210 From 153646-154015 Picked 20-gum-1997 15:04

A534 07-APR-97 R10 FL210 From 153646-154015 *Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:06*

A534 07-APR-97 R10 FL210 From 153646-154015 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:06

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 210
Mean 447.301
Standard dev 0.322486
Max value 448.385
Min value 446.834

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 210
Mean 246.365
Standard dev 0.297391
Max value 247.129
Min value 246.046

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 210
Mean 242.271
Standard dev 1.08112
Max value 243.803
Min value 239.394

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 210
Mean 66.0257
Standard dev 3.40211
Max value 72.2158
Min value 61.5955

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)

No of obs 210
Mean 53.6545
Standard dev 0.101017
Max value 53.6755
Min value 52.6460

PEROXIDE (PPB)

No of obs 210
Mean 0.253067
Standard dev 4.549361e-02
Max value 0.344000
Min value 0.184000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 210
Mean 6386.98
Standard dev 5.20250
Max value 6394.51
Min value 6369.50

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 210
Mean 43.5084
Standard dev 1.662869e-02
Max value 43.5340
Min value 43.4772

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 210
Mean -38.0288
Standard dev 0.116220
Max value -37.8228
Min value -38.2196

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 210
Mean 6.96057
Standard dev 0.442089
Max value 8.64956
Min value 5.97828

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 210
Mean 14.3302
Standard dev 0.735411
Max value 16.0587
Min value 12.9030

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 210
Mean -0.320075
Standard dev 0.667785
Max value 1.03831
Min value -1.34268

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 210
Mean 15.9350
Standard dev 0.785452
Max value 18.2044
Min value 14.5627

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 244.093

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 210
Mean 144.177
Standard dev 11.1118
Max value 158.152
Min value 120.211

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 101.143

A534 07-APR-97 R11 FL170 From 154442-161932 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:11

A534 07-APR-97 R11 FL170 From 154442-161932 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:11

A534 07-APR-97 R11 FL170 From 154442-161932 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 15:09

A534 07-APR-97 R11 FL170 From 154442-161932 Pkalled 20-gum-1997 15:09

A534 07-APR-97 R11 FL170 From 154442-161932 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:11

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 2091
Mean 526.830
Standard dev 0.350426
Max value 528.407
Min value 524.875

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 2091
Mean 256.327
Standard dev 0.551188
Max value 257.602
Min value 255.429

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 2091
Mean 237.476
Standard dev 8.25029
Max value 260.403
Min value 227.139

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 2091
Mean 55.3728
Standard dev 5.88503
Max value 72.8142
Min value 42.5880

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)

No of obs 2091
Mean 53.5808
Standard dev 0.935792
Max value 55.8756
Min value 50.0449

PEROXIDE (PPB)

No of obs 2091
Mean 0.211397
Standard dev 0.132085
Max value 0.616000
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 2091
Mean 5187.00
Standard dev 4.95438
Max value 5214.68
Min value 5164.73

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 2091
Mean 42.9759
Standard dev 0.295083
Max value 43.3799
Min value 42.3938

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 2091
Mean -35.1646
Standard dev 1.16301
Max value -33.2887
Min value -37.2460

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2091
Mean 7.43975
Standard dev 1.74078
Max value 10.7916
Min value 2.52358

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2091
Mean 11.4676
Standard dev 1.57542
Max value 17.1476
Min value 8.78083

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2091
Mean 0.516433
Standard dev 0.505882
Max value 2.66478
Min value -1.68856

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 2091
Mean 13.7560
Standard dev 1.77208
Max value 19.2272
Min value 10.8602

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 237.026

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 2091
Mean 156.653
Standard dev 11.3935
Max value 169.610
Min value 118.215

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 108.760

A534 07-APR-97 P5 FL170-50' From 161932-164009 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 15:12

A534 07-APR-97 P5 FL170-50' From 161932-164009 Potted 20-gum-1997 15:12

A534 07-APR-97 P5 FL170-50' From 161932-164009 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:14

A534 07-APR-97 P5 FL170-50' From 161932-164009 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:14

A534 07-APR-97 P5 FL170-50' From 161932-164009 plotted 9-Aug-1997 12:14

A534 07-APR-97 R12 600' From 164119-164253 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:15

A534 07-APR-97 R12 600' From 164119-164253 *Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:15*

A534 07-APR-97 R12 600' From 164119-164253 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 15:13

A534 07-APR-97 R12 600' From 164119-164253 Plotted 20-gum-1997 15:13

A534 07-APR-97 R12 600' From 164119-164253 *plotted* 9-Jun-1997 12:15

A534 07-APR-97 R12 600' From 164119-164253 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:15

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 95
Mean 1000.04
Standard dev 1.17479
Max value 1002.12
Min value 998.653

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 95
Mean 287.393
Standard dev 8.127501e-02
Max value 287.579
Min value 287.292

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 95
Mean 287.150
Standard dev 6.606313e-02
Max value 287.297
Min value 286.964

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 95
Mean 40.5476
Standard dev 1.34064
Max value 43.8959
Min value 37.8975

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)

No of obs 95
Mean 51.5581
Standard dev 1.04377
Max value 52.7435
Min value 49.3838

PEROXIDE (PPB)

No of obs 95
Mean 0.607579
Standard dev 9.241068e-02
Max value 0.768000
Min value 0.448000

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 95
Mean 172.064
Standard dev 10.1675
Max value 184.199
Min value 153.162

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 95
Mean 41.7958
Standard dev 1.283709e-02
Max value 41.8170
Min value 41.7727

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 95
Mean -31.7667
Standard dev 2.578948e-02
Max value -31.7234
Min value -31.8110

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 95
Mean 9.03449
Standard dev 0.415720
Max value 10.1456
Min value 7.97637

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 95
Mean 3.14508
Standard dev 0.311490
Max value 3.71896
Min value 2.36461

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 95
Mean 0.523806
Standard dev 0.206323
Max value 1.06717
Min value 0.128426

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 95
Mean 9.56888
Standard dev 0.468246
Max value 10.6887
Min value 8.38528

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 199.194

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 95
Mean 96.4111
Standard dev 1.94066
Max value 103.106
Min value 92.8591

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 124.119

A534 07-APR-97 R13 FL070 From 174702-175923 *Plotbed 9-Jun-1997 12:17*

A534 07-APR-97 R13 FLO70 From 174702-175923 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:17

A534 07-APR-97 R13 FLO70 From 174702-175923 Plotted 20-Jun-1997 15:15

A534 07-APR-97 R13 FLO70 From 174702-175923 Plotted 20-Aug-1997 15:16

A534 07-APR-97 R13 FL070 From 174702-175923 Plotted 9-Jun-1997 12:17

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 742
 Mean 784.673
 Standard dev 0.707883
 Max value 788.041
 Min value 784.199

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 742
 Mean 277.739
 Standard dev 0.150557
 Max value 278.051
 Min value 277.496

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 742
 Mean 271.207
 Standard dev 1.36874
 Max value 272.739
 Min value 267.293

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 742
 Mean 42.0230
 Standard dev 2.09100
 Max value 47.3211
 Min value 36.5387

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)
 No of obs 742
 Mean 9.25535
 Standard dev 0.213647
 Max value 9.72478
 Min value 8.99916

PEROXIDE (PPB)
 No of obs 742
 Mean 0.808474
 Standard dev 0.367418
 Max value 1.32800
 Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 742
 Mean 2104.66
 Standard dev 7.23921
 Max value 2109.51
 Min value 2070.24

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 742
 Mean 37.7357
 Standard dev 0.118051
 Max value 37.9455
 Min value 37.5344

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 742
 Mean -26.9605
 Standard dev 0.230565
 Max value -26.5618
 Min value -27.3550

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 742
 Mean -3.56220
 Standard dev 0.783984
 Max value -2.17442
 Min value -4.74411

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 742
 Mean 7.36404
 Standard dev 0.580426
 Max value 8.33405
 Min value 6.17344

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 742
 Mean 0.210622
 Standard dev 0.296896
 Max value 1.15578
 Min value -0.449867

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 742
 Mean 8.22584
 Standard dev 0.452267
 Max value 8.90556
 Min value 7.00083

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 295.814

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 742
 Mean 104.484
 Standard dev 0.665854
 Max value 106.559
 Min value 103.055

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 123.129

Glossary

Aircraft Position, Speed and Attitude

- **Navigation:** The aircraft carries GPS, OMEGA, and inertial navigation systems.
- **Pressure height:** is based on the standard atmosphere as specified by the International Civil Aviation Organisation (sea level pressure of 1013.25 hPa). Pressure height is quoted in terms of Flight Levels (height in hundreds of feet *e.g.* FL100 = 10000 feet).
- **Radar height:** altitude of the aircraft above surface, measured by radar.
- **Time:** All times are UTC.

General meteorology

- **Tephigrams:** are given for every major profile of each flight. A tephigram is a thermodynamic diagram (temperature (T) - entropy (ϕ) diagram) used to assess the static stability of a given atmospheric profile. Other meteorological organisations use similar diagrams such as the Emagram or the Skew T log p diagram.
- **Deiced true temperature:** air temperature with corrections for aircraft speed and altitude.
- **Potential temperature:** the temperature that a parcel of air would have if it follows a dry adiabatic lapse rate to the 1000 hPa level.
- **Dew point:** dew point (the temperature at which a sample of air would just become saturated with respect to a plane surface of water if cooled at a constant pressure) calculated from the chilled mirror General Eastern hygrometer.
- **FWVS Dew point:** dew point calculated by use of the Lyman- α spectroscopic instrument “the fluorescence water vapour sensor”.

Cloud Physics

- **PCASP:** The Passive Cavity Aerosol Sampling Probe counts number concentrations (number per cm^3) of particles in 15 channels spaced pseudo-logarithmically over the diameter range 0.10 μm to 3.00 μm , to provide a particle size distribution over this range.
- **FSSP:** The Forward Scattering Spectrometer Probe is used to measure water droplets in the size range 0.5 to 47.0 μm diameter (cloud droplets). It has four range settings, each of which is divided into 15 size channels.

Chemistry Parameters

- **Ozone:** Calibrated readings from the TECO 49 ozone analyser in ppb. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent (UK Met. Office).
- **JNO₂:** The sum of upward and downward facing radiometers (raw data). Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Sandra Schmitgen (FZ Jülich).
- **Hydrogen peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb (approx.). Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Organic peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb (approx.). Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Modelled peroxide:** hydrogen peroxide concentrations as estimated from the concentrations of ozone and water vapour concentrations according to the following algorithm. The model is used in flight and is included in this data summary for individual scientists assessment of the use of algorithms for the purpose of in flight planning. Contact Brian Bandy, Claire Reeves (UEA, Norwich) or Dave Tiddeman (UK Met. Office) for details.

$$H_2O_2 = (k_3 j_4 [O_3] [H_2O]) / (k_5 [M] (j_6 + k_7 + [OH] k_8))$$

where k_3 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O(^1D) + H_2O \rightarrow 2OH$

k_5 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O(^1D) + M \rightarrow O(^3P) + M$

k_8 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $OH + H_2O_2 \rightarrow H_2O + HO_2$

k_7 is the first order loss due to dry deposition. However, as the boundary layer is difficult to define, this term has been ignored for the time being.

j_4 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O_3 + hv \rightarrow O(^1D) + O_2$

j_6 is the rate coefficient for reaction: $H_2O_2 + hv \rightarrow OH + OH$

j_4 , j_6 and $[OH]$, calculated by a 2D model, are dependent upon latitude and time of year.

- **Formaldehyde:** Raw data recorded as bits. NB this instrument has a long time delay *ca.* 12 minutes. Instrument scientist: Graham Mills (UEA, Norwich).
- **NO_x:** Parameters (NO, NO₂, NO_{y1}, NO₂) were recorded on MRF's data recording system and are plotted in volts. Instrument scientist: Stephane Bauguitte (UEA, Norwich).
- **Bottles:** Please refer to the bottle flight logs (within the flight folder section to see when these were filled). Bottle filler: David Tiddeman (UK Met. Office).
- **Bags/CO analysis:** Please refer to the bottle flight logs (within the flight folder section to see when these were filled). Bottle filler: David Tiddeman (UK Met. Office). Analysis was carried out at ITE Edinburgh by Neil Cape. Plots of CO (ppb) with altitude (pressure height in metres) are included. Contamination has been noted in some of the bag samples, for further advice contact ITE Edinburgh.

ARASF

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